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Mixed Ligand Cobalt(III) Complexes Containing Benzotriazole or 5-Nitrobenzotriazole

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Manuscript received 3 August 1981, revised 6 February 1982,
accepted 27 May 1982

COMPLEXING behaviour of benzotriazole¹⁻⁴ and its use in estimation of some transition metal ions⁵⁻⁷ are well known. Preparation of mixed ligand Co(III) complexes of benzotriazole and of 5-nitrobenzotriazole from *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl and [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂Cl] and their characterization by electronic and ir spectral study and magnetic measurements are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Trans-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl^o, [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)Cl]^o and benzotriazole^o were prepared by reported methods and 5-nitrobenzotriazole was prepared by a modification of the method for benzotriazole.

[Co(en)₂(Bt)*Cl]Cl (rose red) and [Co(en)₂(NO₂-Bt)Cl]Cl (orange red) were obtained by treating an

aqueous solution of [Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl with an aqueous ethanolic solution of benzotriazole and 5-nitrobenzotriazole respectively in 1 : 1 molar ratio and adjusting the pH to 7 with dil. NaOH. [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂(Bt).H₂O (orange yellow) and [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂(NO₂-Bt)].1.5H₂O (dull orange yellow) were prepared in a similar way from [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂Cl]. [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl] 1.2H₂O (orange red) was precipitated by adding a saturated aqueous solution of KI to an aqueous solution of [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl.

Cobalt in the complexes was estimated as cobalt sulphate after igniting the complex and treating the residue with conc. HNO₃ and conc. H₂SO₄. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's semi-micro method. Water of crystallization was determined by heating the complex below 120° and chlorine was estimated as AgCl by decomposing the complex in presence of AgNO₃. C and H analyses were obtained from microanalytical laboratory.

Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Guoy method using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as standard. Effective magnetic moments were calculated after making diamagnetic correction using Pascal's constants¹¹. Conductivity measurements of aqueous solutions were done on a conductivity bridge (Toshniwal, India). Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hilger Watts Uvispek spectrophotometer H700. Infrared spectra (4000-650 cm⁻¹) were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Substitution products from trans-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl: The analytical data of the complexes are reported in Table 1. The complexes are slightly soluble in water but almost insoluble in methanol or ethanol. They are diamagnetic suggesting the presence of octahedral low spin Co(III)¹². Δ_M values of freshly prepared 10⁻³ M aqueous solutions of [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl and [Co(en)₂(NO₂-Bt)Cl]Cl were 125 and 130 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, respectively which are in the range of 1 : 1 electrolytes¹³. The conductance gradually increased on standing which may be due to aquation e.g. [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]⁺ + H₂O = [Co(en)₂(Bt)(H₂O)]²⁺ + Cl⁻.

These complexes show only one weak band around 500 nm (Table 1) except [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl which displays an additional shoulder at 370 nm. The weak band corresponds to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and the shoulder to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transition of low spin octahedral Co(III) complexes¹⁴. Higher λ_{max} values for the solid state than for the solution (Table 1) indicate lower symmetry in solid than in solution. *Cis*- and *trans*-isomers of the complexes of the type [CoA₂BC]²⁺ can be differentiated by ε_{max} values of these bands¹⁵, e.g. ε_{max} values of ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} bands of *cis*-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]⁺ and *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)(Cl)]²⁺ are 89 and 90 compared to 41 and 40 for the corresponding *trans*-complex^{15,16}.

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Complex	Analysis%		${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ band	
	Calcd.	Found	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$
[Co(en) ₂ (Bt)Cl]Cl	Co 16.01	16.11	535 ^d	—
	N 26.74	26.84	500 ^a	117
	Cl 19.26	19.31		
[Co(en) ₂ (Bt)Cl].1.5H ₂ O	Co 11.90	12.01	590 ^d	—
	N 19.78	19.81		
	C 24.23	24.41		
	H 4.88	4.91		
	H ₂ O 7.27	7.02		
	Co 14.27	14.31	540 ^a	—
[Co(en) ₂ (NO ₂ -Bt)Cl]Cl	N 27.12	27.18	500 ^a	128
	Cl 17.17	17.05		
	Co 17.42	17.51	470 ^d	—
[Co(NH ₃) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂ Bt].H ₂ O	N 33.13	33.21		
	C 21.25	21.31		
	H 2.56	2.61		
	H ₂ O 4.23	4.01		
	Co 14.96	15.02	475 ^d	—
	N 32.07	32.18		

d=diffused reflectance, a=aqueous solution.

In the present case, only one isomer has been obtained for each complex and hence such a comparison cannot be made. However, high $\epsilon_{\max}$ values viz., 117 for [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl and 128 for [Co(en)₂(NO₂-Bt)Cl]Cl and similarity in the band structure in these complexes with the *cis*-complexes reported earlier^{1,5,16} indicate *cis*-configuration in these complexes.

The reported diagnostic splittings of NH₂ deformation, NH₂ rocking^{7,18} and also some NH vibration bands¹⁹ cannot be applied in the present case for establishing *cis*- or *trans*-configuration since bands of benzotriazoles interfere in these regions. However, the presence of a large number of bands in the present case and the presence of two -CH₂- rocking modes, viz., 880 and 898 cm⁻¹ for [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl and 872 and 890 cm⁻¹ for [Co(en)₂(NO₂-Bt)Cl]Cl may be indicative of *cis*-configuration in these complexes^{20,21}.

Substitution from [Co(NH₃)₂(NO₂)₂Cl]: These complexes, viz., [Co(NH₃)₂(NO₂)₂Bt].H₂O and [Co(NH₃)₂(NO₂)₂(NO₂-Bt)].1.5H₂O are insoluble in water, methanol, ethanol, benzene or chloroform. They lose water molecules on heating at 100° without change in colour. They are slightly paramagnetic, $\mu_{\text{eff}}=0.71$ B.M. for the former and 0.75 B.M. for the latter. Their residual magnetism may be due to the formation of a little Co(II) or it may be due to second order Zeeman effect²².

The ν_{as} and ν_{s} of NO₂⁻ are observed at 1395 cm⁻¹ and 1330 (and 1318) cm⁻¹ for [Co(NH₃)₂(NO₂)₂(Bt)].H₂O and at 1400 cm⁻¹ and 1332 (and 1308) cm⁻¹ for [Co(NH₃)₂(NO₂)₂(NO₂-Bt)].1.5H₂O. The shift in ν_{as} of NO₂⁻ from 1250 cm⁻¹ in free ion to ~ 1400 cm⁻¹ in the complexes suggest N-bonding of NO₂⁻²³ which is further confirmed by the absence of the characteristic ν_{as} band of nitrito group at 1065 cm⁻¹²⁴. The δ (O-N-O) for

these complexes are observed at 811 and 822 cm⁻¹, respectively. Further, the observed splitting of the ν_{as} band of NO₂⁻ may be indicative of *cis*-arrangement of the two NO₂⁻ groups in the complexes.

It has not been possible to establish deprotonation of benzotriazoles in these complexes from the ir data because of the presence of N-H vibrations arising from ethylenediamine or ammonia. However, the necessity of alkaline medium for the formation of these complexes, their diamagnetic behaviour and their elemental analyses do confirm deprotonation.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn Salts with *o*-Hydroxy Propiophenone and Quinoline

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*Manuscript received 19 May 1981, revised 23 February 1982,
accepted 8 July 1982*

CHEMISTRY of metal β -diketonates has invoked¹ lot of interest in recent years in such diverse areas as spectral studies, gas chromatography, nmr shift reagents, laser technology and as radical initiators in polymerization reactions. The formation of adducts of metal β -diketone chelates plays an important role in the synergistic enhancement of solvent extraction of metal ions. β -Keto esters and *o*-hydroxy carbonyl compounds closely resemble the β -diketonates. It was thought worthwhile to study the reactions of metal salts with *o*-hydroxy propiophenone and quinoline. As a result, this communication reports chelates of *o*-hydroxy propiophenone and their adducts with quinoline.

Experimental

Complexes of the type MLXQ or M' LXQ: Absolute ethanolic solution of metal salts was treated with *o*-hydroxy propiophenone and quinoline in 1:1:1 proportion and the resulting solution refluxed for 30 min. To this solution, dilute ammonium hydroxide was added dropwise under constant stirring till the pH was 7. The resulting precipitates were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum.

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Complexes of the type ML₂Q₂ or M'L₂Q: Aqueous solutions of metal acetates were treated with ethanolic solution of *o*-hydroxy propiophenone in 1:2 proportion and the mixture stirred for 30 min at 40°. Metal chelates were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum. Ethanolic suspension of different metal chelates was treated with quinoline in 1:2 ratio and the resulting solution refluxed for 30 min. On concentrating the solution in a rotary vacuum evaporator and keeping at 10° overnight crystalline base adducts separated. These were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Analyses and physical measurements were done as reported earlier². The relevant analytical data are presented in Table 1 and the spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

In the infrared spectra of hydroxy propiophenone $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is observed³ at 1620 and $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ at 3350 cm^{-1} . In monochelate complexes, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ shifts to lower frequency region and is observed around 1600 cm^{-1} whereas $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ disappears. Thus the ligand anion forms the chelate using both the oxygen atoms. This has been substantiated by the observation⁴ of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ around 440-460, 320-335 and 230-250 cm^{-1} region, respectively. Thus, these are four coordinated compounds involving the mono chelate, the coordinated anion and coordinated quinoline. In the nitrate complexes, the position of ν_4 and ν_1 (1410 and 1280 cm^{-1}) of NO_3 and their difference of the order of 130 cm^{-1} suggest^{5,6} monodentate nitrate coordination.

In the *bis* chelates $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is found around 1590-1600 cm^{-1} which shifts to slightly higher frequency region in the base adducts. The formation of the base adducts of the *bis* chelates has been confirmed⁴ by the appearance of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 460 and 320 cm^{-1} region in the far infrared spectra.

In the visible region, cobalt mono chelate complexes give rise to one intense absorption band around 16.0 kK region assignable⁷ to ${}^4\text{A}_g \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ transition. Position of the band, its high intensity and lower magnetic moment value suggest a possible tetrahedral configuration for these complexes. The base adduct of the *bis* chelate complex gives rise to two absorption bands at 18.8 and a shoulder at 19.5 kK assignable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition. On the basis of the band positions and magnetic moment values an octahedral configuration is proposed for the complex.

Nickel(II) mono chelate complexes are diamagnetic and show one absorption band a 16.5 kK, presumably indicating a square planar configuration for these two complexes, whereas the base adduct of the nickel(II) *bis* chelate gives rise to three absorption bands at 9.5, 13.8 and 24.4 kK